

Document Code	URC-F0-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 1 of 30

**TEMPLATE FORM ON FACULTY FULL-BLOWN PROPOSAL AND OR
FINAL IMRAD (Publishable) MANUSCRIPT**

1. TITLE: In the Eye of the Beholder: Senior High School Learners' Perception of an HEI's Brand Equity

Researchers:

Clara M. Gonzales (Lead Researcher and Corresponding Author, STEH)

Angela Garra (Primary Collaborator, SAB)

Joman Juanino Baliton (Secondary Collaborator, SHANS)

Queen Nessellyn Galicia (Secondary Collaborator, STEH/AAO)

Zuen Azzaleah Tolentino (Secondary Collaborator, STEH)

May 23, 2023

2. ABSTRACT (Up to 250 words or fewer)

Grounded on the social exchange theory of communication, this study aimed to determine the brand equity of Saint Mary's University as perceived by senior high school learners from SMU's feeder schools. The theory postulates that if people feel they can benefit from an engagement despite the costs, they will continue to engage with it. A total of 204 Grade 12 learners comprised the respondents of this study. There were more male than female respondents. The majority were enrolled in public schools; more than one half were in the GAS track, followed by STEM, HUMM, TechVoc, and ABM. One fifth of the respondents preferred BS Criminology, followed by BSN. Top choices also included Hospitality Management, Civil Engineering, IT, Architecture, and Biology. Among the twelve indicators of brand equity, three themes emerged as very important, namely brand trust, supporting-library services, and core-emotional environment. This indicates that a brand's trustworthiness, library services, and the emotional environment are very important to the respondents. The respondents were aware of all the basic information about SMU. However, the highest is their awareness of the different program offerings of SMU, followed by their awareness that the course they intend to enroll is available at SMU, and the location of SMU. The respondents' profile variables are unlikely to be a significant predictor of senior high school learners' perceived importance of brand equity of SMU and their knowledge about SMU. In terms of the benefits of studying in SMU, three emerged as the top themes, namely high passing rates, scholarships, and quality education. In terms of the cost of studying at SMU, the top three themes were tuition fees, financial problems, and course offerings. As a general recommendation, the marketing team of SMU should highlight the salient findings of this study in their marketing communication strategies, especially in the production of the next corporate video of SMU since this is the commonly used promotional material for SMU, both in its internal and external engagements.

3. INTRODUCTION (1 to 2 pages written in single space; maximum of 500 words; Up to 1-4 paragraphs with 5 to 10 references)

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 2 of 30

One of the basic tenets of communication is reciprocity, where efforts are made to fulfill certain expectations (Geuens, Wiejters, De Wulf, 2009). This concept of reciprocity is postulated in the social exchange theory of communication, which forwards the idea that people always consider the costs and benefits of their engagements with others, be it personal, social, or business. Establishing brand equity is a communication strategy that most organizations utilize to promote their services. Brand equity refers to a value premium that a company generates from a product with a recognizable name compared to a generic equivalent (Hayes, 2021). Saint Mary's University, a private Catholic institution of higher learning and operating for 93 years now in Northern Luzon, has etched its image or brand in the province and nearby. This study seeks to determine if the brand equity of SMU, as perceived by its prospective enrollees, the senior high school students in Region 2, matches the image it wants to project as articulated in its marketing communication strategies. Anchored on the social exchange theory of communication, this study seeks to determine if the concept of reciprocity when enrolling in SMU is articulated to senior high school students, who are the prospective enrollees of SMU. The results of this study will be used to enhance the marketing communication strategies of SMU in order to communicate its intended brand to its stakeholders.

As posited by Hayes (2021), brand equity pertains to the value premium of a product or a company. According to Lokken, Nayar, Runering (2012), there are three dimensions used to describe brand equity: brand awareness, brand loyalty, and perceived quality. Brand awareness is a general term that describes a consumer's familiarity or awareness with a brand or its products. It is a measure of how memorable and recognizable a brand is to its target audience (binder.com). Brand loyalty is the tendency of consumers to continuously purchase one brand's products over another. Consumer behaviour patterns demonstrate that consumers will continue to buy products from a company that has fostered a trusting relationship (Skyword, 2022). Perceived quality is the quality of a product or service according to the customer's perception. It is a subjective criterion and does not have to coincide with the actual or objective quality, which is based on tangible data such as raw materials, manufacturing process, warranty, or after-sales service (Armetrics, 2022).

Social Exchange Theory's concept of cost and benefits

According to the social exchange theory, people always consider the costs and benefits before they engage in any relationship, whether in personal, social, or professional contexts. Benefits refer to the plusses one gets from any engagement, while costs refer to the minuses one exerts to maintain the relationship. People make a conscious decision to continue with the engagement after assessing that the benefits outweigh the costs. This concept is the framework used in this present study. A school, specifically a private one like Saint Mary's University, largely depends on the tuition and fees paid by its students to continue its operations. The fees are the benefits that it gets from its students. While the fees are considered benefits for SMU, these are costs for the students. However, they still voluntarily enroll in SMU and pay the tuition because they think the benefits outweigh the costs. The benefits are the quality of education and service that they get from being enrolled here. The relationship also has costs for SMU, as it is challenged to continue improving its services by subjecting itself to different accreditations, training personnel, providing competitive incentive packages to keep its employees, and building facilities to ensure the quality of service. If these benefits are not communicated well to the prospective enrollees, they will not find any reason to enroll in SMU.

This study was undertaken to determine prospective enrollees' perception of SMU as a provider of higher learning. Since these learners do not yet have any direct experience with the

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 3 of 30

services of SMU, they can be a good source of data in determining if the intended message and image articulated in SMU's marketing efforts are the same as the perceived image of SMU as perceived by outsiders, in this case the senior high school students of SMU's feeder schools.

Branding in Higher Education Institutions

Harsha et al. (2011) underscore branding in higher education institutions as the latest focus in education marketing to attract students. Boateng (2014) conducted a study on branding public universities through advertising in Ghana. Using a qualitative approach to gather data, the study revealed six facets of service brand identity: physique, personality, relationship, reflection, culture, and self-image. The study's findings lend credence to these elements to create a brand identity implied by existing brand identity frameworks. The data points to positive results for higher institutions which desire to invest and maintain strong brand identity and image given that these facets influence competition. Boateng recommended that for branding and advertising to effectively promote the image of institutions, a strategically planned branding program is recommended to attract more constituents.

Pindar, et al. (2014), in their study about university brand equity, identified the factors that are important for university branding. Through a review of the literature, they identified brand equity dimensions for university branding, which were classified as core and supporting. The core value creation dimensions identified are brand awareness, perceived quality, brand loyalty, brand association, organizational association, emotional environment, learning environment, and brand reputation. The supporting value-creation dimensions identified are student living, library services, career services, and physical facilities. According to Pindar, et al. (2014), core and supporting factors are essential in establishing a university's brand equity.

In another study conducted by Villanueva et al. (2015), they found that the university's image and reputation remain the primary factors its clients consider in enrolling in the university. The study, which was conducted in SMU, aimed to fortify the university's enrolment management through brand equity assessment.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the social exchange theory of communication. Social Exchange Theory proposes that behaviours can be thought of as the result of cost-benefit analyses by people attempting to interact with society and the environment. If a person believes that they can extract more of a reward through a behaviour than they lose by performing it, then the person will perform the behaviour. Conversely, when the person feels that the cost will outweigh the benefit, the behaviour will not be performed (Jonason & Middleton, 2015). The same principle is applied in marketing communication, especially in building brand equity. When the "benefits" of a brand are not communicated to its intended recipients, the brand will be perceived as a "cost" and hence, will result in the non-patronizing of the brand. Therefore, any two entities who decide to enter into an engagement must have a clear understanding of the costs and benefits of the engagement as these will be the factors that they will consider if they will continue, or terminate, the engagement.

Conceptual and Analytical Framework

Reciprocity of communication is the principal value of this study. Grounded on the social exchange theory of communication, which promotes the idea that two entities in a relationship draw their decision to terminate or continue the engagement based on the principle of

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 4 of 30

reciprocity, this study aims to determine if the respondents, who are the target enrollees of SMU, feel that they can benefit from patronizing the SMU brand.

In order to do this, the profile of the respondents is sought first. Second, their awareness of SMU brand equity is determined, as well as their perception of SMU brand equity. Next, relationships is established between the respondents' profile variables and their awareness and perception of SMU brand equity. Lastly, the perceived costs and benefits of enrolling at SMU is determined. The results of the study may be used to come up with an enhanced marketing communication campaign for SMU.

Statement of the Problem / Purpose of the Study

This study sought to surface the perception of senior high school learners about the brand equity of Saint Mary's University.

Specifically, it sought answers the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - A. Gender
 - B. Type of School Enrolled in
 - C. Senior High School Track
 - D. Course Intended to Enrol in College
2. What is the respondents' assessment of the importance of brand equity in higher education institutions?
3. To what extent are the respondents aware of the basic information about SMU?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their assessment of the importance of brand equity in higher educational institutions?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their awareness of the basic information about SMU?

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 5 of 30

6. What are the respondents' perceived benefits (plusses) and costs (minuses) of enrolling at SMU?
7. What recommendations may be made in the marketing communication strategies of SMU to achieve reciprocity?

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their perception of the brand equity of SMU.
2. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their extent of awareness of the basic information about SMU.

4. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design used in the study is a mixed-methods design that combines both qualitative and quantitative approaches. The quantitative component of the study employs a descriptive-correlational design to investigate the relationship between variables, while the qualitative component uses an open-ended questionnaire to gain a more in-depth understanding of the participants' experiences and perceptions.

Research Locale

The participants came from senior high schools in Nueva Vizcaya, Quirino, Ifugao, and Mountain Province. Based on the data from the Office of the University Registrar in SMU, a large percentage of their feeder schools, both private and public, at the undergraduate level came from these provinces.

Participants and Sample

The participants in this study were 204 Grade 12 learners from the feeder schools of SMU in the previously identified provinces. During the data collection period from February-March 2023, the SMU recruitment team determined the schools to be visited and identified the population of eligible participants who met the inclusion criteria. The study's objective was to determine the brand and image of SMU from the perspective of non-Marians (prospective enrollees), so the study did not include Grade 12 students from SMU. The inclusion criteria specified that only Grade 12 learners who were 18 years old and above and not enrolled in SMU were eligible to participate. Conversely, the exclusion criteria stated that the study did not include Grade 12 students who were 17 years old and below and enrolled in the Senior High School of SMU.

Research Instrument

The primary tool used in the study was a modified survey questionnaire, which included researcher-made items and items adapted from Pindar et al. (2014). The profile of the respondents and the basic information about SMU items were researcher-made, while the items about the overall brand equity were adapted from Pindar et al. (2014).

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 6 of 30

The questionnaire items about basic details on SMU were taken from the 2022 edition of the SMU Bulletin of Information. Villanueva et al. (2015) also used this part of Pindar et al.'s questionnaire in their study on brand equity.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data were gathered from the feeder schools visited by the recruitment team of SMU. The research team sought the permission of the school principal and other concerned school officials to conduct the study. Once approved, the researchers sought the respondents' consent through an Informed Consent Form. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents.

Since the data gathering coincided with the career campaign, the school administration of the feeder schools concerned were informed that apart from the information session, a study on brand equity would also be conducted. The conduct of the study was only done after the information session to those who gave their consent to participate.

Treatment of Data

Descriptive analysis was used to treat the data, specifically the profile of the respondents, their awareness of the basic information about SMU, and their perception of SMU brand equity.

The following scale of interpretation was used for the perceived importance of an HEI's brand equity and degree of awareness about SMU:

Weight	Mean Range	Interpretation (Importance of brand equity)	Interpretation (Awareness)
4	3.50 - 4.00	Very Important	Fully Aware
3	2.50 - 3.49	Important	Aware
2	1.50 - 2.49	Unimportant	Not Aware
1	1.00 - 1.49	Very Unimportant	Not Fully Aware

Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the strength and direction of the relationship between these variables. The profile of the respondents was analyzed in terms of four variables: gender, type of school enrolled in, senior high school track, and course intended to enroll in college. To answer questions 4 and 5, the researchers used chi-square tests to determine if there was a significant relationship between these profile variables and the respondents' assessment of brand equity and their awareness of basic information about SMU.

Thematic analysis was used to establish significant themes regarding the respondents' perception of the costs and benefits of enrolling at SMU.

Ethical Considerations

The study was submitted to Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB), Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, for assessment and approval. The UREB was

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 7 of 30

chaired by Mr. Jason Arnold L. Maslang (email: jamaslang@smu.edu.ph / mobile: 09178787967).

Conflict of Interest

The researchers declared no conflict of interest involved in the study and ensured that no personal gain would affect the study's integrity.

Confidentiality and Data Protection

The researchers complied with the research ethics guidelines of Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board and observed every respondent's confidentiality and data privacy rights. Informed consent was disseminated before the floating of the questionnaire, and the respondents were not forced to participate. The data were personally collected and consolidated by the researchers, saved in a computer accessible only to them, and stored in a personal cabinet. The questionnaire was discarded after the study results were analyzed, presented to, and approved by the University Research Center.

Management of Vulnerability

The researchers were present when the questionnaire was administered to answer questions from the respondents. They assured the respondents that their participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw anytime should they experience discomfort from participating in the study.

Risk/Benefit Ratio

No known risks were involved in the study, contributing to developing knowledge of brand equity and developing a reciprocal relationship between SMU and its stakeholders. Results of the study may have been disseminated to the general public through institutional research fora and other possible venues.

Informed Consent

All respondents included in the study agreed to the informed consent by affixing their signature on the form. The ICF provided details about the purpose and benefits of the study. The students' involvement was voluntary, and their personal information was kept confidential.

Terms of Reference

The researchers were the authors of this study, and no government or funding agencies were involved in it.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1: Profile of the Respondents

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 8 of 30

Table 1. Profile of Senior High School Learners

Profile Variables		Frequency	Percent Count (%)
Gender	Male	105	51.50
	Female	99	48.50
Type of School Enrolled In	Public	187	91.70
	Private	17	8.30
Senior High School Track	Accountancy, Business and Management	6	3.00
	General Academic Strand	107	54.30
	Science, Technology, and Mathematics	38	19.30
	Humanities and Social Sciences	23	11.70
	Technical Vocational and Livelihood	23	11.70
Course Intended to Enroll in College	BS Nursing	26	14.70
	BS Accountancy	1	0.60
	BS Criminology	37	20.90
	BS Architecture	4	2.30
	BS IT	9	5.10
	BS Civil Engineering	12	6.80
	BS Hospitality Management	14	7.90
	BS Biology	2	1.10
Other Courses	72	40.70	

N = 204

Based on the findings, there were 99 female (48.50%) and 105 male (51.50%) respondents.

In terms of the type of school enrolled in, the majority of the respondents were from public schools with 187 (91.70%) while only a small percentage of 17 (8.30%) were from private schools.

Regarding their senior high school track, the findings showed that the General Academic Strand was the most common track (54.3%), followed by Science, Technology, and Mathematics (19.3%), Humanities and Social Sciences (11.7%), Technical Vocational and Livelihood (11.7%), and Accountancy, Business, and Management (3%). This suggests that SMU should tailor its marketing communication strategies to appeal to students in different senior high school tracks, particularly those in the General Academic Strand and Science, Technology, and Mathematics tracks who make up the majority of the respondents. SMU may want to highlight its programs and courses that are related to these tracks in its marketing communication campaign to attract potential enrollees.

In terms of the course intended to enroll in college, the most common course among the respondents was BS Criminology with 37 (20.90%), followed by BS Nursing with 14.7%. Popular choices are also BS Hospitality Management and BS civil Engineering. This may be because the study was conducted in provinces where there is a demand for criminology courses, and other courses may also be popular in the region. It is interesting to note that the respondents who

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 9 of 30

intend to enroll in BS Nursing, which is one of the flagship programs of SMU, only accounted for 14.7% of the total respondents. This indicates that SMU may need to intensify its marketing efforts to increase awareness and interest in its nursing program among senior high school students.

Meanwhile, only a small percentage of respondents expressed interest in enrolling in BS Accountancy, BS Architecture, and BS Biology. This may suggest that SMU needs to review and adjust its marketing communication strategies to attract more students to these programs. It is also worth noting that a considerable number of respondents specified other courses (40.70%), which implies that SMU needs to further explore and understand the factors that influence senior high school students' choice of courses when deciding on their college education.

Section 2: Brand Equity

Table 2: Perceived Brand Equity

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Qualitative Description
<i>Brand Awareness</i>			
1. The university is well-known.	3.33	0.49	Important
2. The university is among the first to come to mind when one thinks of all universities in the country.	3.12	0.57	Important
3. The university's logo is instantly recognizable.	3.27	0.55	Important
4. The university is known to offer specialized degree programs.	3.33	0.48	Important
5. The university's degree programs are well-known.	3.31	0.55	Important
Overall mean	3.27		Important
<i>Perceived Quality</i>			
1. The faculty are knowledgeable in their fields.	3.53	2.15	Very Important
2. The faculty are polite in responding to students.	3.47	0.53	Important
3. The faculty care about students' needs.	3.57	0.52	Very Important
4. The faculty are responsive to student needs.	3.45	0.59	Important
5. The faculty are willing to help students.	3.59	0.50	Very Important
6. The faculty are accessible for students' concerns.	3.49	0.53	Important
7. The university has degree programs offered by few other universities in the country.	3.34	0.55	Important
8. The faculty are engaged in publishing in journals, attending conferences and writing books.	3.30	0.55	Important
Overall mean	3.47		Important
<i>Brand Associations</i>			
1. The university offers experiential learning opportunities (e.g. projects, community works)	3.38	0.50	Important
2. The university employs state-of-the art technology in educating its students	3.32	0.54	Important
3. The university offers an internship (OJT) program.	3.37	0.60	Important
4. The university's career center helps students search for jobs.	3.51	0.52	Very Important
5. The university organizes alumni networking events	3.26	0.54	Important

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 10 of 30

6. The university has intercollegiate athletic teams.	3.20	0.63	Important
Overall mean	3.34		Important
<i>Brand Loyalty</i>			
1. The university is one of the first choices of prospective students.	3.15	0.63	Important
2. Univ.'s graduates recommend the univ. to others.	3.25	0.58	Important
3. The university's graduates are loyal to the university	3.28	0.59	Important
4. The university's graduates are proud of the univ.	3.47	0.57	Important
5. Its students/graduates are proud to have other people know that they will have/or have a degree from the university.	3.44	0.54	Important
Overall mean	3.32		Important
<i>Brand Trust</i>			
1. Students have trust in the education they are receiving/ received from the university.	3.49	0.57	Important
2. The faculty are honest with students.	3.58	0.53	Very Important
3. The faculty and students trust each other.	3.56	0.55	Very Important
4. The faculty emphasize ethical values in their courses.	3.54	0.54	Very Important
Overall mean	3.54		Very Important
<i>Supporting-Facilities</i>			
1. The university offers a career placement with supportive resources (e.g. staff, room, training).	3.47	0.56	Important
2. The university has modern gym facilities.	3.36	0.54	Important
3. The university has modern classrooms.	3.37	0.52	Important
4. The university's library has state-of- art computer labs.	3.49	0.54	Important
5. The university offers a variety of financial aid (e.g. scholarships, student loan, work study) services.	3.50	0.56	Very Important
6. The Registrar's Office takes care of student registration issues.	3.48	0.58	Important
Overall mean	3.46		Important
<i>Supporting- Learning Environment</i>			
1. The university has a supportive learning environment.	3.60	0.54	Very Important
2. The university is known as a respected institution.	3.53	0.53	Very Important
3. The university has high academic standards.	3.45	0.57	Important
4. The university offers well-known degree programs.	3.44	0.58	Important
5. The university has a well-known academic reputation	3.47	0.51	Important
6. Based on the cost of tuition, the university offers a good educational value.	3.46	0.57	Important
Overall mean	3.49		Important
<i>Core-University Reputation (Overall Brand Equity)</i>			
1. The graduates of the university earn higher incomes than industry average.	3.49	2.94	Important
2. Companies prefer recruiting the university's graduates.	3.29	0.58	Important
3. The university's graduates are well- recognized in their professions.	3.40	0.53	Important

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 11 of 30

4. The university's graduates have successful careers.	3.49	0.51	Important
5. The university's graduates receive good job offers.	3.51	0.53	Very Important
6. The university's graduates are employed before or soon after graduation.	3.40	0.57	Important
7. The university's graduates have no trouble getting accepted to graduate school.	3.40	0.60	Important
Overall mean	3.42		Important
<i>Supporting – Library Services</i>			
8. The university has quality library resources (e.g. online databases, journals, books, etc.)	105	51.50	Very Important
9. The library offers a comfortable study environment.	3.55	0.51	Very Important
10. The library personnel are knowledgeable.	3.55	0.53	Very Important
11. The library personnel are polite in responding to student questions.	3.54	0.54	Very Important
12. The library personnel are helpful.	3.54	0.52	Very Important
13. The university provides student tutoring services.	3.50	0.57	Very Important
Overall mean	3.52		Very Important
<i>Supporting-Dining Services/Canteens</i>			
1. The university has clean dining facilities/canteens	3.48	0.52	Important
2. The university dining facility offers healthy food.	3.53	0.53	Very Important
3. The dining service/canteen personnel are knowledgeable about the food they serve.	3.49	0.53	Important
4. The dining service/canteen personnel are polite.	3.48	0.53	Important
5. The dining service/canteen personnel are professional	3.45	0.52	Important
6. The dining service/canteen personnel serves the food quickly.	3.42	0.56	Important
Overall mean	3.48		Important
<i>Supporting-Residence Hall</i>			
1. The university has modern residence halls/dorms	3.36	0.53	Important
2. The university residence halls offer a good environment to study (e.g. study lounge)	3.45	0.52	Important
3. The university residence halls have the latest technology in the rooms.	3.35	0.53	Important
4. The university residence halls provide opportunities for student activities.	3.42	0.53	Important
5. The university residence hall directors are polite.	3.40	0.51	Important
Overall mean	3.39		Important
<i>Core- Emotional Environment</i>			
1. The university provides supportive environment.	3.58	0.56	Very Important
2. The faculty/staff-student interactions are warm.	3.48	0.54	Important
3. Student relationships are characterized as warm and friendly.	3.54	0.52	Very Important
4. The university provided the students with a sense of community.	3.53	0.53	Very Important
Overall mean	3.53		Very Important

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 12 of 30

Brand Awareness

The description of brand equity in terms of brand awareness for SMU includes factors such as well-known university, offering specialized degree programs, well-known degree programs, first to come to mind when one thinks of all universities, and instantly recognizable university's logo.

The item with the highest mean score was "The university is well-known" (mean = 3.33; SD = 0.49), indicating that the respondents highly value the university's overall reputation. This suggests that the university's brand recognition and familiarity are important to prospective students and other stakeholders. The item "The university is known to offer specialized degree programs (mean = 3.33; SD = 0.48;)" received the same high mean score as the item about the university's overall reputation, suggesting that the respondents also highly value the university's offerings of specialized programs. This highlights the importance of the university's unique educational programs as a key component of its brand identity. The item "The university's degree programs are well-known (3.31; SD= 0.55)" was also rated important. The item "The university's logo is instantly recognizable" received a slightly lower mean score (mean = 3.27; SD = 0.55), but was still above 3.0, indicating that the respondents recognize the importance of a recognizable visual identity for the university's brand. Finally, the item "The university is among the first to come to mind when one thinks of all universities in the country" received the lowest mean score (mean 3.12; SD = 0.57) of the five items. However, with a mean score of 3.12, it still falls within the "important" range, suggesting that the respondents consider this aspect of brand awareness to be significant.

The survey results suggest that respondents perceive these elements of brand awareness as important for the university, with all areas evaluated as "important". This aligns with the idea put forth by Keller (1993) that awareness is a critical component in building a brand image. In addition, according to Abbas, S. A. (2019), brand awareness and service quality have a significant impact on brand loyalty of educational institutes; thus, making it compulsory to stress on continuous brand management.

Perceived Quality

Perceived quality for SMU includes knowledgeable faculty in their fields; politeness of faculty; care about students' needs; responsiveness to student needs; willingness to help students, accessible for students' concerns, has degree programs offered by few other universities in the country; and engaging in journal publishing, attending conferences and writing books.

The item that obtained the highest mean score was "The faculty are willing to help students (mean = 3.59; SD = 0.50)" showing that the respondents value very much the faculty members who are helpful. This means that it is very important for the students to have supportive faculty members in their studies. The second-highest item was that "The faculty care about students' needs (mean = 3.57; SD = 0.52)", indicating that students also value so much the faculty members who are concerned and considerate of their needs. This implies that it is very important for the students to have faculty members who are willing to extend their help to them as their need arises, and this is exemplified by our SMU CARES Program. The third with the highest mean was that "The faculty are knowledgeable in their fields (mean = 3.53, SD = 2.15)", which suggests that students also value faculty members who are competent in their fields of specialization. This means that it is very important that faculty members provide them the skills and knowledge they need and that match the needs of the industry. The item "The faculty are accessible for students' concerns (mean= 3.49; SD=0.53)" was perceived to be important. This means that students value faculty members who are available during their consultation hours to cater to their needs.

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 13 of 30

The item *"The faculty are polite in responding to students (mean = 3.47, SD = 0.53)"* means that students also value respectful faculty members, and *"The faculty are responsive to student needs (mean = 3.45, SD = 0.59)"* is likewise perceived as "important". This means that students want faculty members who are approachable when they need help. The item *"The university has degree programs offered by few other universities in the country (mean=3.34; SD=0.55)"* was also perceived as important, and the item with the lowest score was that *"The faculty are engaged in publishing in journals, attending conferences and writing books (mean= 3.30; SD=0.55)." However, it is still perceived as an important element of brand equity because students also need learning resources with local contents.*

Overall, the survey results indicate that respondents perceive these elements of perceived quality as important (mean = 3.47) for the university.

Brand Associations

Brand associations comprise of providing experiential learning opportunities (e.g., projects, community works), employing state-of-the-art technology, offering an internship (OJT) program, helping students search for jobs, organizing alumni networking events, and having intercollegiate athletic teams.

The item that got the highest mean is that *"The university's career center helps students search for jobs (mean = 3.51; SD = 0.52)." This means that it is very important for a university to help its students find employment opportunities after they graduate. The second and third items with the highest scores are "The university offers experiential learning opportunities such as projects and community works (mean = 3.38; SD = 0.50)" and "The university offers an internship (OJT) program (mean = 3.37; SD = 0.60). This implies that it is important for a university to send its students to on-the-job training for them to apply what they have learned in their classes to their actual workplaces. On-the-job training (OJT) is one of the mechanics of the higher education industry in developing the needed competencies of its graduates. Its goals and objectives serve as a guide in developing the needed competencies for a particular job and translating the training into a gainful working experience (Ylagan, 2013, as cited by Bernardo et al., 2014). The item, "The university employs state-of-the-art technology in educating its students (mean = 3.32; SD = 0.54)" was also rated important. This means that students give importance to a university that uses modern equipment and processes in teaching students, such as in laboratories. The university organizes alumni networking events (mean=3.26; SD=0.54), and the university has intercollegiate athletic teams (mean=3.20; SD=0.63), were also perceived as important. This means that students also value linkages such as our linkages with universities abroad for student exchange. In addition, the students also value intercollegiate athletic teams for their social development.*

Brand Loyalty

A university's brand equity in terms of brand loyalty consists of being one of the first choices of prospective students, graduates recommending the university to others, graduates being loyal to the university, graduates being proud of the university, and people knowing that students will have or have a degree from the university.

The item *"The university's graduates are proud of the university (mean = 3.47; SD = 0.57)"* got the highest score. This means that it is important for a university that its graduates are proud to have studied there. *"Saint Mary's University's students and graduates are proud to let other people know that they will have or have had a degree from the university (mean = 3.44; SD = 0.54)"* got the second highest score, which signifies that this item is also important for a university. The item *"The university's graduates are loyal to the university (mean = 3.28; SD = 0.59)"* was also rated as

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 14 of 30

important. This implies that the university is providing quality service to the students. According to Abbas, S. A. (2019), it is the service quality that contributes more to brand loyalty in the long run. The item "*The university's graduates recommend the university to others* (mean = 3.25; SD = 0.58)" was rated important, which implies that students value a university that offers quality education and is therefore recommendable. "*The university is one of the first choices of prospective students* (mean=3.15; SD= 0.63)" was also rated as important, which represents that it is important for students that a university is familiar in terms of offering quality education.

Brand Trust

A university's brand equity in terms of brand loyalty consists of students having trust in the education they are receiving from the university, faculty being honest with students, faculty and students trusting each other, and faculty emphasizing ethical values in their courses.

The item "*The faculty are honest with students* (mean = 3.58; SD = 0.53)" obtained the highest score. This signifies that it is very important for a university that its faculty be morally upright. The item "*The faculty and students trust each other* (mean = 3.56; SD = 0.55)" got the second highest score, which indicates that it is also very important that there is a mutual trust between faculty and students so that students will be motivated to study. The item "*The faculty members emphasize ethical values in their courses* (mean = 3.54; SD = 0.54)" was rated as very important. This implies that faculty should integrate values into their lessons as part of the spiritual development of the students. Finally, the item "*Students have trust in the education they are receiving or received from the university* (mean = 3.49; SD = 0.57) was rated important. This indicates that it is important for a university that its students are confident that they are getting a quality education and that they can find a job easily after graduation.

Brand trust is defined as feeling secure during interactions with a brand based on the perception that the brand is reliable and responsible for the interests of the consumer (Delgado-Ballester et al., 2003, as cited by Budiyono, R., & Novandalina, A., 2022). It is usually defined in two ways. The first refers to consumer willingness to rely on a brand (Chaudhuri and Holbrook, 2001, as cited by Budiyono, R., & Novandalina, A., 2022). The second one refers to the reasons for such reliance on the brand as capacity and intentions in fulfilling its promises to consumers (Dalzeil et al., 2011; Delgado-Ballestrand et al., 2001, as cited by Budiyono, R., & Novandalina, A., 2022).

Supporting-facilities

The description of brand equity in terms of supporting facilities entails offering a career placement with supportive resources, having modern gym facilities, modern classrooms, a library with state-of-the-art computer laboratories, offering a variety of financial aid services, the registrar's office taking care of student registration issues.

The item, "*The university offers a variety of financial aid* (e.g., scholarships, student loans, work study) services (mean = 3.50; SD = 0.56)" was rated as important. This means that it is very important for the university to help the students augment their educational fees. Also important is the item, "*The university's library has state-of-the-art computer laboratories* (mean = 3.49; SD = 0.54)". This is also important for a university so that the students will be updated on the use of new technologies. The item "*The registrar's office takes care of student registration issues* (mean = 3.48; SD = 0.58)" is important because the registrar's office is in charge of the enrolment and records of the students. The university offers career placement with supportive resources (e.g., staff, room, training) (mean = 3.47; SD = 0.56), such as the Alumni Affairs Office of SMU. The university has modern classrooms (mean = 3.37; SD = 0.52), and the university has modern gym

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 15 of 30

facilities (mean = 3.36; SD = 0.54), which are likewise important so that students can have a conducive environment for learning.

In general, three items were rated as very important among the indicators of brand equity. These are brand trust, supporting-library services, and core-emotional environment. This result indicates that the learners value a University's honesty and ethical standards in its delivery of quality education. Also, the learners also find important that the library services are of quality, including the comfort of the study environment, and friendliness, knowledge, and politeness of the library staff. This is probably because the library is a study space for students to make their assignments and projects and to research about their lessons. A supportive environment, characterized as warm and friendly, is also important to the learners probably because such environment provides them with a sense of community. Such kind of environment supports students not just academically but more importantly, emotionally.

Section 3: Basic Information about SMU

Table 3: Basic Information About SMU

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Qualitative Description
1. I am aware that SMU offers programs in basic education (grade school, junior high school senior high school).	3.09	0.74	Aware
2. I am aware of the undergraduate courses offered at SMU.	2.74	0.71	Aware
3. I am aware that SMU offers post-graduate studies (MA and PhD) and juris doctor.	2.75	0.78	Aware
4. I am aware that the course I intend to enroll in college is offered at SMU.	3.04	0.75	Aware
5. I am aware of the program accreditations of SMU.	2.82	0.66	Aware
6. I am aware of the location of SMU.	3.03	0.79	Aware
7. I am aware of the cost of tuition at SMU.	2.61	0.86	Aware
8. I am aware of the different modes of transportation to get to SMU.	2.89	0.76	Aware
9. I am aware that SMU has a website where I can access relevant information about the school.	2.88	0.73	Aware
Overall mean	2.84		Aware

The item "I am aware that the course I intend to enroll in college is offered at SMU" (mean = 3.04; SD = 0.75) got the highest score. This means that the students are aware of the courses being offered by SMU, maybe because of the career campaigns being conducted and its website and Facebook accounts. The second item with the highest score is "I am aware of the location of SMU (mean = 3.03; SD = 0.79)", which signifies that they are aware of SMU's location as discussed during the career campaigns. Next is the item "I am aware of the different modes of transportation to get to SMU (mean = 2.89; SD = 0.76)" which implies that they are aware of how to get to the University. This is followed by the item "I am aware that SMU has a website where I can access relevant information about the school (mean = 2.88; SD = 0.73)", which implies that they are also

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 16 of 30

aware of the social media accounts of SMU. The other items are still within the awareness level, which are the statements: "I am aware of the program accreditations of SMU (mean = 2.82; SD = 0.66); I am aware that SMU offers post-graduate studies (MA and PhD) and juris doctor (mean = 2.75; SD = 0.78); I am aware of the undergraduate courses offered at SMU (mean = 2.74; SD = 0.71); and I am aware of the cost of tuition at SMU. (mean = 2.61; SD = 0.86); Overall, the respondents are aware about the basic information about SMU (mean = 2.84).

Section 4: Significant relationship between the respondents’ profile variables and their assessment of the importance of brand equity in higher educational institutions

Table 4: Relationship between the respondents’ profile variables and their assessment of the importance of brand equity

Computed p-value on the relationship of...	Profile Variables			
	Gender	Type of School	Senior High School Track	Course Intended to Enroll in College
Brand Equity of Saint Mary’s University	0.45	0.86	0.92	0.86

Null Hypotheses

1. Male senior high school learners and their female counterparts do not have the same perception of the importance of brand equity of SMU. Equivalently, there is no difference in the perception of the importance of brand equity of SMU between males and females.
2. Senior high school students from public and private institutions do not have the same perception of the importance of brand equity of SMU. Equivalently, there is no difference in the perception of the importance of brand equity of SMU between students from public and private senior high school institutions.
3. STEM and Non-STEM senior high school students do not have the same perception of the importance of brand equity of SMU. Equivalently, there is no difference in the perception of the importance of brand equity of SMU between senior high school STEM and Non-STEM students.
4. Whatever course senior high school students intend to enroll in college may not mean that they have the same perception of the importance of brand equity of SMU. Equivalently, there is no difference in the perception of senior high school learners on the importance of brand equity of SMU and the courses they intend to enroll in college.

It was shown in the table that the computed p-value between the importance of brand equity of SMU and gender of senior high school learners is equal to 0.45. This means that we have to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. In like manner, a p-value of 0.45 suggests that there is no statistically significant relationship between brand equity of SMU and gender of students. Also, this means that there is no evidence to suggest that the gender of senior high school learners is associated with their perceived importance about brand equity of SMU.

Meanwhile, a p-value equal to 0.86 was computed between the relationship of the learners’ perceived importance of SMU’s brand equity and the type of school. This means that the null

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 17 of 30

hypothesis stating that there is no relationship between the two, will not be accepted. This may mean that whichever school they came from, either a private or public high school institution, they have relatively perceived or not the importance of the brand equity of SMU. Moreover, brand equity of the university does not depend on the type of school where respondents came from.

In terms of the relationship between senior high school tracks and brand equity of SMU, the computed p-value is equal to 0.92. It can be observed that the calculated p-value is greater than the preferred significance level of 0.05, which means that the null hypothesis should be rejected.

This suggests that the awareness of senior high school learners about the importance of brand equity of SMU is relatively the same among them, whichever track they enrolled in high school.

Furthermore, the relationship between brand equity of SMU and the course that the respondents intend to enroll in college has a p-value of 0.86. This means that researchers have to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. This suggests that there is no evidence to suggest that senior high school students' perceived importance of the brand equity of SMU is associated with the course they intend to enroll in at the university. In like manner, this suggests that whichever course senior high school learners prefer to enroll in college, it has no relationship with their perceived importance on the brand equity of SMU.

The same with the basic information of senior high school learners about SMU. It is important to note that all of their profile variables have no statistically significant p-values. It can be inferred that their profile variables do not necessarily mean that they have or do not perceive the brand equity of SMU to be important. Although the calculated p-value indicates that there is not a statistically significant relationship between the profile variables and brand equity of SMU, it does not necessarily mean that there is no relationship between these variables (their profile variables and brand equity of SMU).

In general, the results of correlation tests suggest that their profile variables are unlikely to be a significant predictor of senior high school learners perceived importance of brand equity of Saint Mary's University.

Section 5: Significant relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their awareness of the basic information about SMU

Table 5: Relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their awareness about SMU

	Profile Variables
--	-------------------

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 18 of 30

Computed p-value on the relationship of...	Gender	Type of School	Senior High School Track	Course Intended to Enroll in College
Basic Information about Saint Mary's University	0.58	0.51	0.09	0.74

Null Hypotheses

1. Male senior high school learners and their female counterparts do not have the same awareness on the basic information about SMU. Equivalently, there is no difference in the level of basic information about SMU between males and females.
2. Senior high school students from public and private institutions do not have the same awareness on the basic information about SMU. Equivalently, there is no difference in the level of basic information about SMU between students from public and private senior high school institutions
3. STEM and Non-STEM senior high school students do not have the same awareness on the basic information about SMU. Equivalently, there is no difference in the level of basic information about SMU between senior high school STEM and Non-STEM students.
4. Whatever course senior high school students intend to enroll in college may not mean that they have the same awareness on the basic information about SMU. Equivalently, there is no difference in the level of basic information about SMU and the courses they intend to enroll in college.

Using the correlation tests, the computed p-value between the basic information about Saint Mary's University (SMU) and gender is equal to 0.58. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected and accept the alternative hypothesis. Equivalently, a p-value of 0.58 suggests that there is no statistically significant relationship between Basic Information about SMU and gender. In other words, there is no evidence to suggest that the gender of senior high school learners is associated with their knowledge or understanding of basic information about SMU.

On the other hand, a p-value equal to 0.51 was computed between the relationship of basic information about SMU and the type of school. This also means that the null hypothesis stating that there is no relationship between the two, will be rejected. This may mean that whichever school they came from, either a private or public high school institution, they have relatively basic information about SMU. Moreover, their knowledge or awareness about SMU does not depend on the type of school where they came from.

In terms of senior high school tracks, these were categorized into five, namely STEM, GAS, TVL, ABM, and HUMSS. However, the data is not normally distributed. Thus, researchers recoded the tracks into two – the STEM and non-STEM tracks. Based on this, the senior high school track and basic information about SMU of senior high school learners have a computed p-value equal to 0.09. It can be noted that it is higher than the desired p-value (<0.05), which leads the researchers to reject the null hypothesis. This means that the awareness of senior high school learners about the basic information of SMU is relatively the same among them, whichever track they enroll in high school.

Moreover, the relationship between the basic information about SMU and course intended to enroll in college has a p-value of 0.74. This means that researchers have to reject the null hypothesis. It can be inferred that there is no evidence to suggest that senior high school students'

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 19 of 30

knowledge or understanding and awareness of the basic information about SMU is associated with the course they intend to enroll in college. Equivalently, this suggests that whichever course senior high school learners prefer to enroll in college, it has no relationship with their awareness of SMU.

It is important to note that all profile variables of senior high school students and their awareness or basic information about SMU have no statistically significant p-values. Meaning, their profile variables do not necessarily mean that they have or do not have information about the offerings of basic education, undergraduate and post-graduate studies, program accreditations, location, cost of tuition, transportation options, and the availability of relevant information on its website. However, the computed p-value does not necessarily mean that there is no relationship between these variables (their profile variables and basic information about SMU), but rather that any relationship that may exist is not statistically significant.

Generally, the results of correlation tests suggest that their profile variables are unlikely to be a significant predictor of knowledge of senior high school learners about SMU, and other factors should be considered when exploring differences in knowledge or awareness of the institution.

Section 6: Perceived benefits (plusses) and costs (minuses) of enrolling at SMU

Table 6: Perceived benefits of enrolling at SMU

Specific Themes	Frequencies
1. High passing rate	11
2. Scholarships	8
3. Quality education	7
4. Well-known university	4
5. Improvement of skills	4
6. Top performing university	3
7. Combination of life insurance and financial protection	3
8. Opportunities	2
9. Graduation	2
10. Unique programs/courses	2
11. Faculty, students and staff	
12. Supportive school	1
13. Job prospects	1
14. Overseas job opportunities	1
15. LGBT-friendly policies	1
16. Branding	1

Sixteen themes emerged as the perceived benefits of studying in SMU.

High passing rate in board exams: This theme has the highest frequency and is likely significant to the respondents. This indicates that the respondents find it important that the school they will choose for their college education has high passing rates in board exams. A high passing rate suggests that the university has a strong academic program and can provide quality education, which is attractive to prospective students. This may also indicate that they intend to enroll in board courses rather than non-board courses.

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 20 of 30

Scholarships and quality education: These themes have relatively high frequencies (8 and 7 respectively) and indicate that affordability of education is significant to the respondents, as well as the value and quality education. Scholarships can provide financial assistance and make education more affordable, reducing the burden of tuition fees.

Well-known university and improvement of skills: These themes have moderate frequencies (4) and may be beneficial in terms of improving job prospects. A well-known university that improves one's skills can enhance the reputation of students' education and increase their chances of finding employment.

Top performing university and combination of life insurance and financial protection: These themes have moderate frequencies (3) and highlight the importance of a university's performance and its ability to provide financial protection. A top performing university with a high employment rate indicates that students are more likely to find jobs after graduation.

Opportunities and graduation: These themes have a moderate frequency (2) and may refer to various opportunities such as internships, research projects, or networking opportunities provided by the university, which can enhance a student's overall educational experience, leading to graduation.

Faculty, students, and staff: This theme has a low frequency (1) and suggests that a warm and friendly environment created by faculty, students, and staff may be a relatively minor benefit for students.

Supportive school, job prospects, overseas job opportunities, LGBT-friendly policies, and branding: These themes have low frequencies and may be considered as minor benefits or may not be applicable to all students, depending on their individual needs and interests.

Table 7: Perceived costs of studying at SMU

Themes	Specific Costs	Frequencies
1. Tuition Fees	Expensive tuition fees	8
2. Financial Problems	Financial problems, expenses	8
3. Course Offerings	Not offering desired course, no idea of cost, etc.	7
4. Living Expenses	Living expenses, transportation	6
5. Financial Stability	Financial stability of family, not enough budget, etc.	5
6. Distance from Home	Far from home	4
7. Discount/Scholarship	Discount system, scholarship offers	4
8. Emotional Problems	Emotional problems, high standard of education	2
9. Commuting Hassle/ Transportation	More expensive and hassle in commuting	2
10. Cost of Enrollment	University costs, expensive tuition fees	2
11. Miscellaneous	Miscellaneous	2
12. Other Expenses	Food, shelter	1
13. High Expectations/Pressure	High expectations, pressure	1

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 21 of 30

Fourteen themes emerged as the perceived costs of studying at SMU.

Tuition fees and financial problems: The themes of expensive tuition fees and financial problems are mentioned by eight respondents each, indicating that cost of tuition is a significant concern for students and suggesting that students face challenges related to their financial situation.

Course offerings: Seven respondents mentioned not being offered their desired course or having no idea about the cost, indicating that course availability and associated costs are factors influencing their decision.

Living expenses: Six respondents mentioned living expenses and transportation as specific costs, indicating that the overall cost of living is a consideration for students.

Financial stability: Five respondents mentioned concerns about the financial stability of their family and not having enough budget, highlighting the impact of financial factors on their decision-making process.

Distance from home: Four respondents mentioned being far from home as a specific cost, suggesting that the location of the university and associated costs such as travel expenses are taken into account.

Discount/Scholarship: Four respondents mentioned the availability of discount systems and scholarship offers, indicating that financial incentives play a role in their decision-making process.

Emotional Problems: Two respondents noted emotional problems and high standard of education, suggesting that psychological factors may impact their decision-making process.

Commuting hassle/transportation: Two respondents said commuting being more expensive and a hassle, indicating that transportation-related costs and inconvenience may be a consideration.

Cost of enrollment: Two respondents noted university costs and expensive tuition fees, reinforcing the significance of cost as a factor in decision-making.

Miscellaneous: Two respondents mentioned miscellaneous factors, which could include any other specific costs not covered in the other categories.

Other expenses: One respondent said food and shelter as specific costs, highlighting that students consider various other expenses beyond tuition fees.

High expectations/pressure: One respondent cited high expectations and pressure, indicating that academic expectations and pressure may affect their decision.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

- a. **Respondents Profile.** A total of 204 Grade 12 learners comprised the respondents of this study. Out of the 204 respondents, there are more male than female respondents. The majority are enrolled in public schools; more than one half of them are in the GAS track, followed by STEM, HUMM, TechVoc, and ABM. One fifth of the respondents intend to enroll in BS Criminology, followed by BSN. Top choices also include Hospitality Management, Civil Engineering, IT, Architecture, and Biology. Many also intend to enroll in other courses.
- b. **Respondents' assessment of the importance of brand equity.** Among the twelve indicators of brand equity, three themes emerged as very important, namely brand trust, supporting-library services, and core-emotional environment. Nine were rated as important, namely brand awareness, perceived quality, brand association, brand loyalty, supporting-facilities, supporting-learning environment, core-university reputation,

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 22 of 30

supporting-dining services, and supporting-residence halls. This indicates that a brand's trustworthiness, library services, and the emotional environment are very important to the respondents. It is therefore recommended that these indicators be highlighted in the University's promotion efforts, especially in the corporate video which is often used to introduce SMU in all its local, national, and international engagements.

- c. **Respondents' Awareness of the basic information about SMU.** The respondents are aware of all the basic information about SMU. However, the highest is their awareness of the different program offerings of SMU, followed by their awareness that the course they intend to enroll is available in SMU, and the location of SMU.
- d. **Significant relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their assessment of the importance of brand equity.** The respondents' profile variables are unlikely to be a significant predictor of senior high school learners' perceived importance of brand equity of SMU.
- e. **Significant relationship between the respondents' profile variables and their awareness of the basic information about SMU.** The respondents' profile variables are unlikely to be a significant predictor of knowledge of senior high school learners about SMU. Other factors should be considered when exploring differences in knowledge or awareness of the institution.
- f. **Perceived benefits (plusses) and costs (minuses) of enrolling at SMU.** In terms of the benefits of studying in SMU, three emerged as the top themes, namely high passing rates, scholarships, and quality education. In terms of the cost of studying at SMU, the top three themes are tuition fees, financial problems, and course offerings.
- g. **Recommendations to achieve reciprocity between SMU and its prospective students.** The goal of every partnership is reciprocity. In the relationship between SMU and its primary stakeholders who are the students, this reciprocity should be evident. Therefore, the marketing team of SMU should highlight the salient findings of this study in their marketing communication strategies, especially in the production of the next corporate video of SMU since this is the commonly used promotional material for SMU, both in its internal and external engagements.

References

Abbas, SA (2019). Brand loyalty of higher education institutions. *Marketing and Management of Innovations*, 1, 46-56.

Bernardo, A. C., Landicho, A., & Laguador, J. M. (2014). On-the-job training performance of students from ab paralegal studies for SY 2013-2014. *Studies in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 1(4), 122-129.

Boateng, A. (2014). *Branding public universities through advertising: A study of two public universities in Ghana*. University of Education, Winneba.

Hayes, A. (2021). *Brand Equity: Definition, Meaning, Effect on Profit Margin, and Examples*. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/b/brandequity.asp>

Document Code	URC-F0-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 23 of 30

Jonason, P. & Middleton, J. (2015). Dark Triad: The “Dark Side” of Human Personality. *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/social-sciences/social-exchange-theory>

Lokken, A., Nayar, M., & Runering, M. (2012). *Brand equity – measuring corporate brand strength in the Swedish smartphone market: Dimensions of corporate brand equity from a consumer perspective*. Beling Institute of Technology.

Pervan, S. and Johnson, L. (2002). *Interpreting value in relationship marketing: A social exchange theory perspective*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/41385501>

Pinar, M., Girard, T., Trapp, P., & Boyt, T. (2014). University brand equity: An empirical investigation of its dimensions. *International Journal of Educational Management*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267625843>

Villanuerva, H., Palina, J., Garra, A., and Martin, N. (2015). *Fortifying the university's enrollment management through brand equity assessment*. Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya: Saint Mary's University.

What is brand awareness? Retrieved from binder.com

What is perceived quality. Retrieved from <https://www.arimetrics.com/en/digital-glossary/perceived-quality>

Yucel-Aybat, O., Gibney, R., Masters, M. F., & Amlie, T. (2018). A social exchange perspective on student retention and university support intentions. *Philanthropy & Education*, 1(2), 1–27. DOI 10.2979/phileduc.1.2.01

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 24 of 30

Appendix

Informed Consent Form

This form is for the Grade 12 students from the feeder schools of Saint Mary's University to participate in the research titled "In the Eye of the Beholder: Senior High School Learners' Perception of an HEI's Brand Equity."

Name of Researchers Clara M. Gonzales
Joman Juanino Baliton
Queen Nesselyn Galicia

Organizational Affiliation Saint Mary's University
School of Teacher Education and Humanities
Department of Languages

Information Sheet

You are being invited by faculty researchers from Saint Mary's University to participate in their study titled "In the Eye of the Beholder: Senior High School Learners' Perception of an HEI Brand Equity." Since your privacy is respectfully recognized, all information gathered will not be disclosed to anyone other than the researchers who are involved in the research study. All the data collected will be treated with utmost confidentiality following the Data Privacy Act. You will be assigned a numerical code to protect your identity. The accomplished questionnaire will be kept in a personal cabinet accessible only to the researchers. The data will be kept for a period of one year, on once the

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 25 of 30

University Research Center has given a data clearance and approved the final study. The data will be disposed by tearing the pages until the contents are not recognizable.

Your participation in this research study will contribute to developing knowledge on brand equity and developing a reciprocal relationship between SMU and its stakeholders. Your participation, however, is optional and voluntary. You may participate in our study or decline anytime you feel uncomfortable.

Should you choose to participate in the study, you shall be answering a questionnaire that will take around 15-20 minutes to answer. There is no known psychological risk involved in the study, and there is no direct benefit to you either. You shall not receive any payment for your participation nor any reimbursements. There is, however, a possible health risk involved as the data gathering will be done face-to-face. To mitigate the risk, we assure you that we will comply with the minimum health requirements of SMU and of your school in terms of hand washing, wearing of face mask, and social distancing. We will also bring with us our own alcohol for hand sanitation if there is a need to use one during the data gathering.

Even if you have chosen to participate voluntarily, you have the right to refuse to continue, and any information you have already provided will not be used in the study.

For any concern related to the study, please contact the lead researcher:
Clara M. Gonzales 09262110443 cgonzales@smu.edu.ph

Certificate of Consent

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it, and any questions I have asked were answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____ Date: _____

Research Questionnaire

A. Profile of the Respondents. Please put a check mark or write your answer in the corresponding blanks. Please do not leave any items unanswered for all the items in this questionnaire.

1. Gender: Male Female
2. Age: _____ (Note: Only 18 years old and above should answer this questionnaire)
3. Name of School: _____
4. Type of School Enrolled in: Public Private
5. Province: _____
6. Senior High School Track: ABM GAS STEM HUMMS

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 26 of 30

___ Arts and Design ___ Others (specify) _____

7. Course You Intend to Enrol in College: _____

B. Respondents' Awareness of Basic Information About SMU. Below are items about Saint Mary's University. Please put a check mark in the box that corresponds to your level of awareness about each item.

Basic Information About SMU	Fully Aware 4	Aware 3	Not Aware 2	Not Fully Aware 1
1. I am aware that SMU offers programs in basic education (grade school, junior high school senior high school).				
2. I am aware of the undergraduate courses offered at SMU.				
3. I am aware that SMU offers post-graduate studies (MA and PhD) and juris doctor.				
4. I am aware that the course I intend to enroll in college is offered at SMU.				
5. I am aware of the program accreditations of SMU.				
6. I am aware of the location of SMU.				
7. I am aware of the cost of tuition at SMU.				
8. I am aware of the different modes of transportation to get to SMU.				
9. I am aware that SMU has a website where I can access relevant information about the school.				
10. What else do you know about SMU?				

C. Respondents' Perception of a university's brand equity. Below are items about a university's brand equity. Please put a checkmark on the box that corresponds to the degree to which you find each item about a university brand equity important or unimportant.

Overall University Brand Equity	Very Important	Important	Unimportant	Very Unimportant
Brand Awareness				
1. The university is well-known.				
2. The university is among the first to come to mind when one thinks of all universities in the country.				
3. The university's logo is instantly recognizable.				
4. The university is known to offer specialized degree programs.				
5. The university's degree programs are well-known.				
Perceived Quality				

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 27 of 30

6. The faculty are knowledgeable in their fields.				
7. The faculty are polite in responding to students.				
8. The faculty care about students' needs.				
9. The faculty are responsive to student needs.				
10. The faculty are willing to help students.				
11. The faculty are accessible for students' concerns.				
12. The university has degree programs offered by few other universities in the country.				
13. The faculty are engaged in publishing in journals, attending conferences and writing books.				
Brand Associations				
14. The university offers experiential learning opportunities (e.g. projects, community works)				
15. The university employs state-of-the art technology in educating its students				
16. The university offers an internship (OJT) program.				
17. The university's career center helps student search for jobs.				
18. The university organizes alumni networking events				
19. The university has intercollegiate athletic teams.				
Brand Loyalty				
20. The university is one of the first choices of prospective students.				
21. Univ.'s graduates recommend the univ. to others.				
22. The university's graduates are loyal to the university				
23. The university's graduates are proud of the univ.				
24. Its students/graduates are proud to have other people know that they will have/or have a degree from the university.				

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 28 of 30

Brand Trust				
25. Students have trust in the education they are receiving/ received from the university.				
26. The faculty are honest with students.				
27. The faculty and students trust each other.				
28. The faculty emphasize ethical values in their courses.				
Supporting- Facilities				
29. The university offers a career placement with supportive resources (e.g. staff, room, training).				
30. The university has modern gym facilities.				
31. The university has modern classrooms.				
32. The university's library has state-of- art computer labs.				
33. The university offers a variety of financial aid (e.g. scholarships, student loan, work study) services.				
34. The Registrar's Office takes care of student registration issues.				
Supporting- Learning Environment				
35. The university has a supportive learning environment.				
36. The university is known as a respected institution.				
37. The university has high academic standards.				
38. The university offers well-known degree programs.				
39. The university has a well-known academic reputation				
40. Based on the cost of tuition, the university offers a good educational value.				
Core- University Reputation (Overall Brand Equity)				
41. The graduates of the university earn higher incomes than industry average.				

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 29 of 30

42. Companies prefer recruiting the university's graduates.				
43. The university's graduates are well-recognized in their professions.				
44. The university's graduates have successful careers.				
45. The university's graduates receive good job offers.				
46. The university's graduates are employed before or soon after graduation.				
47. The university's graduates have no trouble getting accepted to graduate school.				
Supporting – Library Services				
48. The university has quality library resources (e.g. online databases, journals, books, etc.)				
49. The library offers a comfortable study environment.				
50. The library personnel are knowledgeable.				
51. The library personnel are polite in responding to student questions.				
52. The library personnel are helpful.				
53. The university provides student tutoring services.				
Supporting – Dining Services/Canteens				
54. The university has clean dining facilities/canteens				
55. The university dining facility offers healthy food.				
56. The dining service/canteen personnel are knowledgeable about the food they serve.				
57. 10. The dining service/canteen personnel are polite.				
58. 11. The dining service/canteen personnel are professional				
59. The dining service/canteen personnel serves the food quickly.				
Supporting- Residence Hall				

Document Code	URC-FO-50
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 30 of 30

60. The university has modern residence halls/dorms				
61. The university residence halls offer a good environment to study (e.g. study lounge)				
62. The university residence halls have the latest technology in the rooms.				
63. The university residence halls provide opportunities for student activities.				
64. The university residence hall directors are polite.				
Core - Emotional Environment				
65. The university provides supportive environment.				
66. The faculty/staff-student interactions are warm.				
67. Student relationships are characterized as warm and friendly.				
68. The university provided the students with a sense of community.				

D. Costs and Benefits of Enrolling in Saint Mary's University

1. What do you consider are the benefits (plusses) of enrolling at Saint Mary's University?

2. What do you consider are the costs (minuses) of enrolling at Saint Mary's University?

Thank you so much.